

High Speed Reactive Processing of Thermoplastic Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polyamide-6 Composites

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Carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP)

Applications

- **Light-weight material**
 - High mechanical strength w/ low density
cf. HSS (High strength steel), Mg/Al
 - Transportation (aerospace, automotive, ...)

Boeing 787 Dreamliner

Density - Strength of Materials
Materials Selection in Mechanical Design by Michael F. Ashby

Lightweight Material	Material Replaced	Mass Reduction (%)	Relative Cost Per Part
Magnesium	Steel, Cast Iron	60 - 75	1.5 - 2.5
Carbon Fiber Composites	Steel	50 - 60	2 - 10+
Aluminum Matrix Composites	Steel, Cast Iron	40 - 60	1.5 - 3+
Aluminum	Steel, Cast Iron	40 - 60	1.3 - 2
Titanium	Steel	40 - 55	1.5 - 10+
Glass Fiber Composites	Steel	25 - 35	1 - 1.5
Advanced High Strength Steel	Mild Steel	15 - 25	1 - 1.5
High Strength Steel	Mild Steel	10 - 15	1

Light-weight materials
U.S. Department of Energy

Polymer Matrix

Thermoset CFRP

- Mainly epoxy
 - Curing process (time-/cost- consuming)
- Properties
 - Brittle
 - Polymer does not melt (cross-linked)
 - Repair/recycle is difficult
 - (Relatively) low viscosity

Thermoplastic CFRTTP

- Polyamide, Polypropylene, polyethylene, ...
 - No curing process required
- Properties
 - Ductile (E absorption ↑ , safety)
 - Polymer melt w/ heating
 - **Welding / post-process / Repair / recycle**
 - (Relatively) high viscosity

Various type of FRP
<http://www.rapidcomposites.com>

Thermoplastic/Thermoset structure
<http://www.recycledplastic.com>

Epoxide Group

Polyamide (PA)

Why polyamide (PA-6)?

- **Advantages**

- High performance
- Availability
- Low cost
- Low monomer viscosity
- Low processing temperature

→ PA-6 CFRTP

Thermoplastic matrix	Processing temperature [°C]		Temperature reduction [°C] (reactive vs. melt processing)
	Melt processing	Reactive processing	
PA-6	230-290	140-160	70-150
PA-12	230-270	180-245	0-90
PBT	250-270	180-200	50-90
PMMA	220-260	120-160	60-140
PC	265-360	250	15-110
PET	265-325	250-325	0-15
PES	330-390	300	30-90
PPS	330	300	30
PEEK	380-390	350	30-40

Processing Temperature of thermoplastics

Kjelt Van Rijswijk Thesis (Delft university)

Performance of various thermoplastic

<http://www.dupont.com/>

Property	PA-4	PA-6	PA-12
Methylene:amide ratio	3	5	11
Melting point [°C]	260	223	180
Density [g/cm ³]	1.18	1.13-1.15	1.01-1.02
Equilibrium moisture content at 100% RH	28	9.5	2.0
Glass transition temperature [°C]:	-	65	58
	100% RH	-22	42
Flexural strength [MPa]:	-	113	56
	50% RH	40	40
Flexural modulus [GPa]:	-	2.7	1.4
	50% RH	1.0	1.0

Properties of various polyamide

Kjelt Van Rijswijk Thesis (Delft university)

Challenges

- **High-viscous Thermoplastic**

- Polymer: High viscosity
- Monomer: low viscosity → Good for processing (Even less viscous than thermoset epoxy)

→ **Reactive processing**

- **Poor interfacial interaction btw CF & thermoplastic**

- Most carbon fibers are sized for thermoset
- Proper sizing material for CFRTP is required

→ **Sizing material for thermoplastic**

Processing condition of various composite

Composites: Part A 38 (2007) 666–681

Processing

- **Carbon fiber coating with the sizing material**

- Carbon fiber: TR3110 (Mitsubishi. Inc.)
- Sizing material
- Dip-coating

- **Reactive processing**

- Prepare caprolactam melts & Metal mold with carbon fiber inside
- Injection → Impregnation → Polymerization
⇒ PA-6 CFRTP

Schematic diagram of reactive processing

PA-6 CFRTP Processing time

- Composite Manufacturing Video Recording

- 01:12 Resin injection
- 01:43 Resin flow out from the outlet
- 02:19 Outlet closed (injection completed)
- 04:14 Inlet closed
- 04:50 Removed from hot press
- 05:32 Demolding (3 min. 13 sec. after injection)

Polymerization time < 3 min. 13 sec.

* According to DSC measurement results, 95% of the reaction is completed within 2.95 minutes.

Mechanical Properties of PA-6 CFRTTP

- **Inter-laminar shear, Tensile, Compressive Properties** 3.0mm, 50% CF V_f
 - ILSS: 37.3 MPa → 45.3 ~ 49.9 MPa (~33.8% ↑)
 - Tensile strength: 596 MPa → 604 ~ 641 MPa (~7.6% ↑)
Tensile modulus: 40.5 GPa → 49.7 ~ 67.1 GPa (~65.7% ↑)
 - Compressive strength: 141 MPa → 152 ~ 238 MPa (~68.8% ↑)

→ Less usage of CFRP ↓ & Price ↓ & Light-weight ↑

From left, ILSS(ASTM D2344), Tensile(ASTM D3039), Compressive(ASTM D3410) Mechanical properties

Electric Vehicle Battery Case Component

- Target component: Battery case lower plate (1/2 scale)
 - Thermal analysis based on the original component (AL, CFRP, AL/CFRP)
 - The temperature for CFRP is too high, so **Al/CFRP hybridization is necessary.**

Component Design & Mold

Al/CFRP hybrid case (half)

Mold (upper/lower)

Aluminum case

CFRP case

Al/CFRP hybrid case

Al/CFRP Hybrid Battery Case

Al/CFRP Hybrid Battery Case

- Al/CFRP Hybrid Battery Case Manufacturing (CFRP / CFRTTP)
 - Thermosetting epoxy-based CFRP
 - Reactive processing thermoplastic PA-6 matrix-based CFRTTP
 - ~4.58kg (33%) weight reduction
 - Additional weight reduction possible (fiber lamination structure optimization)

Weight reduction effect > Weight reduction cost

Left) Original component
Right) Al/CFRP hybrid component

original component and
Al/CFRP hybrid component

Post-Processing, Maintainability & Recyclability

Post-Processing, Maintainability & Recyclability

- Post-processing and maintainability using thermoplasticity
 - Sheet-type intermediate → **Compression molding**
 - Additional heating w/ pressure → **Improves Vf & surface impregnation**
 - *PA-6 Film viscosity: ~230 Pa·s within 250–260.5°C temperature range.
 - Solvent solubility
 - Insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, or organic solvents
 - Dissolves in formic acid and sulfuric acid.
- **Carbon fiber recycling possible via acidic solvents.**

Excellent recyclability/processability.

Sheet-type CFRTP

Post-processing

↓ 8 hours

Dissolution of the CFRTP

PA-6 viscosity

Conclusion

- Thermoplastic PA-6 CFRTP were successfully manufacture by high speed reactive processing
- The sizing material was developed to enhance the interfacial interaction between the carbon fiber and PA-6 matrix produced by reactive processing.
- The PA-6 CFRTP reactive processing was applied to EV battery case component.
- Post-processing, maintainability, and recyclability of the produced PA-6 CFRTP were evaluated.

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Reference

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Thank you for your kind attention

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